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Governing by prototype and proto-practice: topological configurations of future classroom labs

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ABSTRACT

The study of topological policy cultures highlights a tendency in policy spaces to undo the effects of topographical and cultural distances and differences. In contemporary education policy trends, such traits are present in the attempts to reimagine classroom spaces. A case in point is Future Classroom Lab (FCL), a physical classroom concept developed and spread across Europe, which promotes the use of digital technologies and divides the classroom into different functional 'zones'. We analyse FCL as a prototype that incites open exploration in the use and design of classrooms. We argue that prototypes are sometimes equally morphing into *proto-practices*, which are *practised* forms of prototypes that are in constant flux, enabling new and different functions, meanings and emotions to emerge. Prototypes and proto-practices secure the continuous transformation of policy spaces through relatively open variation, differentiation and exploration. As such, they are emblematic of contemporary topological policy cultures.

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Introduction

It is a widely held view amongst education policy scholars that contemporary policy cultures have become increasingly topological. This means thinking about and acting on society in terms of mobility and overcoming topographic and cultural distances and differences in economic areas, socio-technical infrastructures, and information and communication networks (Decuyper, Hartong, and van de Oudeweetering 2022; Lury, Parisi, and Terranova 2012; Saari 2022). Topological models and metaphors, such as networks and clouds, are frequently used in policy discourses to illustrate how the topographically distant in space can be brought near and present, or how differences in policies can be overcome through standardization (Gulson and Sellar 2019; Lewis 2021; Ruppert 2012).

Topological policy cultures are prominent, for instance, in network governance, which embodies the tendency to think about and act on education and society in terms of self-organizing 'networks' which penetrate and make diffuse boundaries between public and private sector actors (Ball 2016; Kabir 2021; Rowe 2023). In network governance,

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network metaphors can create a sense of natural connection, freely flowing communication and frictionless mobility of people, information and objects, and the overcoming of ‘boundaries’ between institutions and topographical space-times (Frankham 2006; Hartong 2016; Saari and Sääntti 2018). The recent emergence of data infrastructures in policy networks is a case in point. Data infrastructures link up heterogeneous forms of hardware, digital software, statistical processes and policies into (temporarily) stabilized assemblages. They are seen to enable organizations to leverage advanced technologies such as artificial intelligence, machine learning, and predictive analytics, which aid in overcoming of topographical boundaries and the enactment of topological time and space (Gulson and Sellar 2019; Hartong and Förschler 2019; Kitchin 2014). This way, topological policy cultures are also relevant to the study of policy mobilities in its focus on how policies cross multiple scales from global to national, local and personal, and how policies are reproduced, repurposed, altered or resisted (Ball 2016; Lewis 2021).

What is rarely acknowledged, however, is that topological policy cultures do not only operate across large topographical distances; they are also imbued with decidedly local spaces that are equally ‘becoming topological’ (Decuyper and Lewis 2023; Lewis and Decuyper 2023; Lury 2021; Lury, Parisi, and Terranova 2012). For instance, during the last decade, classroom environments and school architecture in various countries are argued to be endowed with topological characteristics: novel spatial arrangements in schools are designed to support flexible uses of physical spaces and instructional technology based on the latest research on learning (Saari 2022). This takes the form of building reconfigurable classroom spaces for different learning activities by equipping classrooms with portable walls and furniture, as well as facilitating the use of digital devices. These spaces are frequently thought to ‘open’ the confines of the traditional school institution to contemporary modes of communication such as group work, especially in information-intensive work (Saari 2022, 885–6). Topological policy culture is prominent here as a tendency to think about and act on physical classrooms with the idea of overcoming existing spatiotemporal (i.e., topographical) constraints and frictions in education, in order to establish more ‘flexible’ learning (Saari 2022.). Moreover, such spaces are imagined and designed to be imbued with other topological spaces, such as virtual learning environments, data infrastructures, and national and international policy spaces of evaluation. While the push for decisively reorganising classroom spaces has been a recurring theme in global and national education policy arenas for many decades now (Braster et al. 2011), there is currently an exceptionally strong agenda, funding and infrastructure in global policy organisations (e.g. European Commission 2013; Krafl et al. 2022; OECD 2013; Peña-López 2017; UNESCO 2017), for a profound restructuring of physical classroom spaces in response to global trends of digitalization and 21st-century skills.

A case in point of such developments is the *Future Classroom Lab*, a platform hosted by European Schoolnet – a non-profit organisation composed of 34 European Ministries of Education that aims to innovate teaching and learning. The aim of Future Classroom Lab (henceforth FCL) is to “bring innovation in teaching and learning to (...) key stakeholders” and ‘to support education stakeholders in Europe in the transformation of education processes for 21st-century digitalized societies’ (European Schoolnet, 2017). These stakeholders include a wide range of educational and research institutions, European ministries of education, educational administrators, and educators, as well as

30 industry partners (European Schoolnet 2023). In line with the topological policy characteristics outlined above, FCL classroom design seeks to overcome the material and technological limitations to learning characteristic of ‘traditional’ classroom spaces; that is, those with pupils seated behind rows of desks, facing the teacher (European Schoolnet, 2017). Established in 2012 in Brussels, the development of FCL classrooms has spread around the EU under the concept of ‘learning labs’. Learning labs are considered as “independent initiatives, often inspired by the original Future Classroom Lab created by European Schoolnet in Brussels. Learning Lab Classrooms in different geographical locations represent similar ideas, but each site is given freedom and encouraged to make its own adjustments (European Schoolnet 2023). The freedom of making adjustments in different locations captures a particular register of meaning in the term *topological* policy cultures, as topology refers to the study of continuous transformation in space.

The rise of topological policy cultures is coterminous with two recent trends in policy studies. First, there is a new focus on contemporary discourses and techniques of governance imbued in topological concepts, metaphors and ways of enacting them (Decuyper, Hartong, and van de Oudeweetering 2022; Lury, Parisi, and Terranova 2012; Saari 2022). Second, there have been theoretical and methodological approaches developing topology into a useful analytical lens for studying how contemporary policy cultures transcend topographical borderings and forms of localization through continuous change (Allen 2016; Decuyper 2021; Saari 2012). Our article taps on both research trajectories, as we will study FCL as a specific manifestation of policy culture and develop topological tools for studying how it manifests continuous change, as prototypes and proto-practices.

Our argument unfolds as follows. In the first section, we advance the concepts of prototypes and proto-practices and the ways they express specific forms of topological policy cultures. We then present the FCL prototype as it was designed by the European Schoolnet. By acting as *feasible utopias*, such prototypes encourage variation and transformation through reaching out towards future forms of classroom design and teaching. We show how this takes place through examining the case example of a Finnish FCL network of teacher training schools. More specifically, we look at how the original FCL prototype is turned into a Finnish version of that prototype according to perceived national and institutional exigencies. In the last two analytic sections, we examine the case of one FCL classroom environment, KAKS10 (FCLab Tampere). This brings to the fore the detailed sociomaterial and emotional interfaces through which prototypes turn into proto-practices when there is actual teaching and interacting being established in the prototyped classroom. In the concluding section, we reflect on the distinctive character of governing through prototype and proto-practices in relation to network governance.

Prototypes and proto-practices

Jiménez (2014, 343) describes the prototype as ‘an emerging sociomaterial design for our contemporary whose main quality is its permanent “beta” condition; that is, whose social and material components retrofit each other as being in mutual suspension’. The prototype constitutes a sociomaterial configuration – a coming together of material design and social ideas, habits, and customs integrated in this design – based on many iterations of design and further refinement that eventually align into a ‘more

or less durable' form (Suchman, Trigg, and Blomberg 2002, 163). In technological contexts, prototypes are introduced to explore the extent to which they align with established technologies and sites where these technologies are deployed. 'Insofar as it is successful', Suchman et al. argue, 'the prototype works as an exemplary artefact that is at once *intelligibly familiar* to the actors involved, and *recognizably new*' (Suchman, Trigg, and Blomberg 2002, 164., our emphases).

We deploy the notion of the prototype as an analytical device to understand how educational sites are governed through 'intelligibly familiar, yet recognizably new' (ideas about) contemporary classroom environments. In that sense, we understand the notion of the prototype not as referring to singularly bounded technological artefacts (such as the computer or the smartboard) that are newly 'invented', or as innovations that radically break with what was given before. On the contrary, when introduced into schools, new architectural ideas and designs are never just 'dropped' there, as if they can be simply 'plugged into' the existing educational architecture. Instead, when introduced in concrete social settings, such ideas and designs are ongoingly assembled. The prototype is in 'permanent beta', and 'never quite reaches closure (it is always less than itself, less than one) yet it keeps bifurcating and enabling novel extensions of itself (it is always more than its own self-scaling, it is more than many forms of itself)' (Jiménez 2014, 348). It is in that sense that we propose to use the term prototype to not only refer to (the first preliminary version of) a single, bounded invention, such as a smartboard or a printer. Instead, prototypes need to be considered as assemblages of concepts, (architectural) visions, ideas, visualizations, and infrastructural configurations that, once entering a certain specific social site, enact newly emerging types of *practices*. *Proto-practices*, then, are 'practices that are not yet realized but rather are proposals for future practice that are "in the making" and yet grounded in existing practice' (Pandey, 2016: 363). Proto-practices at once express and transform the idealized socio-technical imaginaries that are embedded in prototypes (e.g. with respect to what classrooms and the education of the future should look like) as much as they are re-configuring present-day pedagogies and didactics. In that sense, exactly because they act *in* and *as* practice, they are equally *lived in* and *inhabited* by, for instance, teachers and students. As such, proto-practices possess the unique feature that they do not implement new design(s) in top-down fashion; instead, they give practices a (contingent) shape and form based on the specificities of the local context in which they are implemented.

In line with the topological principle of continuous change, our understanding of prototypes and proto-practices points to the creation of new, partially shared imaginaries that have concrete social (e.g. didactical) and material (e.g. architectural) consequences, without requiring that these ideas be *homogeneously* shared by all new adopters. Prototypes thus have the ability to convey particular ideas and norms *on*, *in*, and *as* practice – and this without wanting to unilaterally seek or aspire to impose those ideas and norms on its users. This implies that prototypes are highly performative devices: by means of their capacity to instill and instigate these ideas in practice, and by showing that these ideas are *feasible utopias* towards which one can aspire and strive, they *imagine* and *invent* user needs (Suchman, Trigg and Blomberg, 2002). It is in that sense that prototypes are at once decidedly real *and* not-yet-fully-realized, for their effective realization is contingent upon how eventual users will enact them into their own existing practices (e.g. as a teacher), both ideal and real (see also Pantzar and Shove 2010).

In that regard, an aspect that has been left unscrutinized in studies of prototypes is the role of emotions in the mobility and transformation of proto-practices. In our field work with an FCL classroom, we stumbled upon the fact that especially when there are no explicit guidelines on how to ‘use’ an unfamiliar FCL prototype, emotions seem to play a central role in how proto-practices are formed. Much has been written about the political aspects of emotions, and how governing seeks to achieve its objectives through inciting, channeling and inhibiting particular emotions (Gagen 2015; Player-Koro, Bergviken Rensfeldt, and Selwyn 2018; Zembylas 2022). There is also an emerging research area on policy mobilities which identifies the crucial role of emotions in the mobility and transformation of policies (McKenzie 2020). Such research frequently emphasizes the performativity of emotions: emotions are not only located ‘in’ the psyche of individuals, but as Ahmed (2013) highlights, they also circulate between individuals and have particular relational effects. They form categories of people and things, endowing them with forces of attraction or repulsion. As emotions circulate, separate and connect things, they also function as a ‘connective tissue’ that links experiential geographies of the human psyche and physique with(in) broader social geographies of place (Davidson and Milligan 2004, 524). In other words, they are inextricably linked to how places are encountered, sustained, and altered (Laketa, 2018). For instance, architectural spaces have the capacity to evoke and disseminate different emotions such as fear and awe (Goldberger 2022; Nye 1996; Kraftl, 2007), and it is this architectural capacity of instilling and circulating emotions – from exhilaration over the new to uncanniness where the experience of disorienting environments elicits awe and anxiety. We pay special attention to how emotions play a significant role in structuring, enacting, and sustaining proto-practices in the classroom. That is to say, the classroom evokes emotions such as excitement and fear in a way that can alter movement and pedagogical interaction in an unpredictable fashion.

In order to understand how prototypes and proto-practices act and function as emblems of topological policy cultures, we first analyzed websites and documents on the European Initiative of FCL. In a second step, we analyzed how the prototype traveled and was adopted by a Finnish initiative called KAKS10 (FCLab Tampere) – a ‘future learning space’, where the FCL prototype, first, found local adoption and was transformed into a Finnish prototype that second, transformed into a proto-practice for teachers in training and teacher educators in a teacher training school at Tampere University. Based on three interviews with the country ambassador and the KAKS10 designers, eight individual and group interviews with student teachers teaching in the classroom, as well as a week-long series of classroom observations of how the KAKS10 prototype functioned as a proto-practice, we were able to analyze how the FCL prototype settled into a Finnish policy culture, and the specific ways in which the eventually originating proto-practice can be considered as being emblematic of contemporary topological policy cultures.

The European prototype: future classroom lab

The very concept *Future Classroom Lab* bears a decidedly future-oriented character: the concept claims to be not just different from mainstream classroom designs, but to be representative of and an incubator for ‘future classrooms’. This entails, on the one hand,

embodying a shared idea of the role of digital technologies in future societies, and on the other, of the need to invent, test and learn in a network to produce an educational form of that future in new types of classrooms. FCL was created as a prototype that visualizes how classrooms could be reorganized and given form according to the principle of *learning spaces*, which refers to a

physical space that supports multiple and diverse teaching and learning programmes and pedagogies, including current technologies; one that demonstrates optimal, cost-effective building performance and operation over time; one that respects and is in harmony with the environment; and one that encourages social participation, providing a healthy, comfortable, safe, secure and stimulating setting for its occupants. (Kuuskorpi and González, 2011)

In the original FCL prototype, learning spaces are organized into *learning zones*, each of which is built to exemplify ‘specific areas of learning and teaching and helps to rethink different points: physical space, resources, changing roles of student and teacher, and how to support different learning styles’ (European Commission 2013, 1). Zones represent normative ideas regarding what good education and good teaching should entail and consist of: being connected, being involved, and being challenged’ (European Commission 2013, 1). At once describing and prescribing, each zone has a dual role to play: a zone *represents* types of learning and interaction identified by the designers and *incites* its audience to take action in rethinking and rebuilding learning spaces for themselves. In sum, whether as a designer, policymaker or as an educator, adopting a zonal ‘mindset’ is not a merely instrumental, imposed or unilateral endeavor, but is from the very start taking place in (as well as shaped by) a loosely ‘regulative, normative, cognitive, and imaginary framework’ (Sørensen and Torfing 2007).

The FCL is indeed not a fixed prototype, but – as a permanent beta version – develops over time. In 2014, the zones were graphically displayed as follows (Figure 1):

In this version of the prototype, each zone was envisioned and designed to be strictly demarcated from other zones. Next to providing a general design idea, in 2012, the FCL

Figure 1. Brussels FCL classroom in 2014 (European Schoolnet 2022).

has equally physically constructed such a prototype classroom space in Brussels. The main idea of this future classroom is to provide a physical, real-life classroom prototype in which educators, policymakers and industry partners can derive inspiration to rethink future forms of learning.

After a major renovation in 2019, the Brussels FCL zonal design has been reconfigured and makes explicit use of overlap between the different zones (see [Figure 2](#)).

Both visualizations highlight that FCL classrooms should be considered as learning spaces where innovative and flexible pedagogy are explicitly given a central position, where the organization of the classroom is responsive to the needs of the teachers and pupils and they can easily move between zones. Such a design allegedly models the quotidian use of (digital) technologies outside the school: ‘flexible learning space enables the student to be mobile and learn at school as they do in everyday life using technologies’ (Bannister 2017). In sum, in the FCL classroom design, there is a strong topological vocabulary in use, highlighting the flexibility and connectivity of the prototype, as well as the need to overcome spatial limitations.

However, topological aspirations are not expressed in the usual form of removing spatial *differences* (cf. Saari and Sääntti 2018). The idea is explicitly not to provide a big homogeneous classroom space where ‘everything could be possible’. Instead, the idea is to build a *catalogue of different zones*, with dedicated purposes, available for easy access and flexible use according to teachers’ and pupils’ varying needs.

As stated above, after the construction of this prototype classroom, over 100 ‘future classrooms’ have emerged, inside and outside the EU (European Schoolnet 2023). Each classroom across these topographic locales operates according to the same general design ideas of dividing the classroom into zones. Zonal topologies have thus extended their reach in the way new types of classrooms are imagined and constructed. Designers on each site are encouraged to explore and make their own adjustments, and FCL intends to offer support where needed. Hence, instead of working according to a logic of

Figure 2. The Brussels classroom since 2019 (European Schoolnet 2022).

standardization, FCL actively encourages other contexts to de-/transform the European FCL prototype and *absorb* it into one's own topological environments (ibid.).

Moving on to examine the original FCL prototype as one set of variations in a national frame, in 2018 the Finnish universities created FCLab.fi, 'to test and develop new learning environments and landscapes' (Future Classroom Lab n.d.). FCLab.fi was inspired by the original FCL design ideas outlined above. Like other FCL sites, FCLab.fi has multiple industry partners. Local university labs also work in collaboration with comprehensive schools and administrators in their respective areas. This taps into a recent rationale in Finnish comprehensive school network governance: the focusing on cultivating of 'ecosystems', characterized by coordinating and facilitating cooperation between state and municipal officials, research institutions, think-tanks, companies (e.g. edtech, media, furniture), etc (Seppänen, Thrupp, and Lempinen 2020).

Finnish FCL environments are built within academic teacher training schools. The Finnish FCL network now has prototype 'labs' in all nine universities, some of which cover multiple learning spaces in the school, and each lab has the triple task of teacher training, research, and innovation (fclab.fi). It communicates new ideas to future teachers about how to teach, operates as a research environment for new teaching practices and technologies, and is intended to inspire administrators in the surrounding municipalities to rethink how new classrooms can be built or old ones renovated. (Ambassador interview). This exemplifies how variations on the original version of the prototype do not necessarily need to rely on the 'original' plan as a sole point of reference: prototypes may inspire ever new variations.

Prototypes also entail the capacity to morph in relation to their surroundings. In an ambassador interview, we were informed about how the Finnish network envisions the specifics of the national context. The ambassador mentioned a great respect for the autonomy for teachers and principals as unique to Finland. According to him, these features are constitutive of how FCLab.fi encourages change in Finnish schools. The ambassador further stated that many Finnish teachers seem to be tied to 'old', 'traditional' ways of teaching. For him, this also applies to student teachers whose original models of what it means to be a teacher included 'traditional classroom spaces' with 'traditional teacher roles', and then carry these expectations into their teacher training. These expectations include an attachment to classroom spaces with a teacher situated at the front and pupils facing the teacher. They also entail teacher-centered modes of instruction with little time and space for pupil co-work and individual freedom (Ambassador interview). Such putative differences between 'new' and 'old' teaching are regularly repeated in the imaginaries of Finnish education policy discourses, where they become annexed to the problem of how to persuade autonomous teachers to adopt new instructional methods and make full use of new learning environments (Saari 2022; Saari and Sääntti 2018).

Thus, in order to extend its topological reach, FCL evokes and makes use of national policy cultures; or, put differently, that the extension of *topological* reach is made more expansive by and contingent upon drawing on ideas, pedagogies and policy traditions considered *topographically* distinct (Decuyper and Lewis 2023; Grommé and Ruppert 2020). This is emblematic of topological power, operating through more subtle registers that do not necessarily have the tendency to 'impose' strict models on other practices. Indeed, the free 'folding' and 'distorting' of prototypical elements and their interrelations

ensures, rather than threatens, the ability to exert power over (educational) timespaces (Allen 2016; Decuyper, Hartong, and van de Oudeweetering 2022).

The Finnish prototype: KAKS10

KAKS10 is a future classroom situated in Tampere University teacher training school, built in 2017 on an empty space of ca. 200 m². Its design was conceived by two teacher educators who were given *carte blanche* with respect to how to construct and give shape to the classroom. Based on their own experience as teacher educators and researchers and inspiration drawn from their visit to the Belgian FCL prototype, they came up with a floor plan that divides the space into ‘zones’ according to different pedagogical activities. It was only after a major part of the classroom was constructed that they joined the FCL network and adjusted how they named and represented the zones and organized the space. In addition to the European Schoolnet model, the teacher educators mention the Finnish national core curriculum and its pedagogical aims as reference points for their zonal differentiation. Very much subscribing to the main characteristics of prototypes as elaborated above, teacher educators added that while much has already been accomplished, KAKS10 is never considered a finished project, but under constant development and revision (Teacher educator interview 1).

The zones in KAKS10 are (Future Classroom Lab, n.d. – see [Figure 3](#)):

- EXPLORE: project work and ‘data processing’
- IMMERSE: activities requiring silence and concentration
- INFLUENCE: pupil presentations, games and use of media.
- EXPRESS: drama and physical exercise
- CREATE: arts and crafts

In our study of KAKS10, the ‘create’ zone was never in use, since it is physically situated in a different room and needs to be booked through a different system – and is hence considered as a ‘different’ classroom rarely mentioned as part of KAKS10.

As can be seen in [Figure 3](#), the two explore zones are placed next to, and partly overlapping with, the immerse zones. Explore and Immerse zones are mostly furnished with chairs and tables. Both these areas also include two large touch screens and two computer desks. KAKS10 houses three other separate Immerse zones, two of which were furnished with couches, a small shelf with books and partition walls. The last Immerse area can be found at the bottom left, a small 6 m² room with glass walls, a computer desk, table and shelf. Lastly, the Influence and Express zones are again zones that partly merge, forming one area with an amphitheater of seats and cushions facing a big TV screen and a checkered floor which also functions as a performance area.

The KAKS10 design stresses the easy movement and flow of teachers and pupils into different zones. For the teacher educators, this is an easier way of organizing pupils into different activities, especially as they consider that they had plenty of square meters at their disposal for the purpose (Teacher educator Interview 1). In distributing these zones across the classroom space, the two teacher educators, when designing the prototype, paid special attention to comfort and acoustics. A point of reference here was the negative press of ‘open plan office classrooms’ in Finland as being noisy, restless and crowded

Figure 3. KAKS10 floor plan (FCLab.fi 2022).

(Teacher educator Interview 1). Taking these concerns into account, in KAKS10 there are zones that are deliberately put into separate rooms, as well as zones separated by partition walls, over which an adult can see. (Teacher educator Interview 1).

What is again apparent, is that the European FCL prototype is not directly applied to the Finnish context: even though both employ a zonal logic and are related to each other, it is equally very clear that *they can link together through being different*. There is no unidirectional influence from the European FCL prototype to the KAKS10 prototype, as it combines elements from the Finnish curriculum, their own experiences and many local exigencies.

As Suchman, Trigg and Blomberg (2002: 174) note, prototypes are ‘polysemous’ in that they can be ‘made to speak in different voices for different audiences’. The prototype is also a ‘mediating artefact’ (Suchman, Trigg and Blomberg 2002) in that it is both formed in and translates the relations between designers and users – sustaining and making use of their differences. In its current form, KAKS10 highlights such aspects as it has multiple functions.

First, KAKS10 is frequently used as a prototype to inspire other prototypes. It is a showcase for visitors – business partners, principals, administrators and researchers

from different countries – as a site where future forms of pedagogy and new classroom technologies and furniture may be experimented with (Teacher educator interview 1). For instance, since a visit by a principal and some teachers from a nearby city, the room and its zonal differentiation have become an inspiration for innovating a whole, fully renovated school in that city along the KAKS10 zonal principles. (Teacher educator interview 2). Second, tech and furniture companies provide their products for field testing in KAKS10. The KAKS10 webpage (www.tuni.fi/norssi/kaksio56/) lists a total of 14 cooperating companies, both national and international. (Teacher educator interview 1). Third, the space operates as an actual classroom for teaching, as two groups of around 20 pupils each (grades 5 and 6) are taught in this class. Its fourth purpose is to train student teachers. Unlike in most classrooms in Finnish schools today, there are sometimes two student teachers for each group of pupils. In addition to polysemy, these functions again testify to the aforementioned claim that prototypes travel by transforming, assuming variations and different roles. It also highlights the aforementioned ‘multiplier effect’ in that the Belgian FCL prototype does not function as the sole point of reference, but instead, prototypes beget new prototypes and proto-practices and/or are assimilated into others to bring together new kinds of actors and inspire ever new variations.

KAKS10 as proto-practice

Next, we focus on the ways student teachers encounter, and act in, KAKS10 - thereby themselves contributing to the enactment of a proto-practice. The orientation towards future learning in KAKS10 teacher training comes from the idea of simulating the Finnish classroom environments of the future. The teacher educators state that as most new schools under construction or major renovation in Finland now employ open and flexible learning spaces and pair teaching, it would require special reasons not to simulate that in a teacher training school (Teacher educator interview 1). Moreover, preparing the students to make full use of the traditional Finnish principle of teacher autonomy is mentioned as a significant guiding principle (Teacher educator interviews 1 and 2).

Student teachers have a total of four periods of teaching practice on their master’s degree program. The students we observed and interviewed, trained in KAKS10 for periods of four to eight weeks. Upon introducing the classroom and discussing the aims and working methods of the teaching practice, the teacher educators reportedly abstained from discussing the existing zones, their definitions and purposes. This was done to avoid overwhelming the student teachers with too much information and to let them explore the possibilities of the classroom autonomously and with an open mind (teacher educator interviews 1 and 2). Interviews with student teachers corroborated the teacher educators’ claim: when we showed them the classroom floor plan with zonal markings, most of them claimed they had never seen it and were not familiar with the rationale of zones. The student teachers reported receiving technical guidance on the use of digital devices, but not much else before they started planning their lessons.

This open exploration is another variant of the way in which prototypes operate as an ‘open code’. Here, the proto-practice is enacted as a *teaching* practice not so much via textual or visual representations of its prototypical governing ideas, but rather through a personal encounter with the space itself (Marres 2012). The material and technological

makeup of KAKS10 is indeed open to many different teaching methods. Yet, of course, not everything is possible: one might say that the material elements of KAKS10 comprise a ‘program’ (Latour 1990), opening and delimiting the range of potential actions to be taken. The material and technological design of the room, together with the school timetables and the school subjects of each lesson, structured a range of different pedagogical methods from frontal teaching to reading and writing alone to presentations and group work.

How, then, did the student teachers make sense of such a space without explicit pedagogical guidance? When we asked the student teachers in interviews about their overall impressions of the classroom space, topological features were clearly discernible in their accounts. The most frequent adjective and characterization attached to the overall classroom plan was that it is ‘more flexible (than most classrooms)’ (Robin). This adjective became connected to the idea of ease in teaching so that, for example, flexibility allows (in the context of COVID-19) hybrid teaching. Moreover, for many students, it is easier to ‘run around’ as a teacher; and easier to ‘manage’ the classroom. Topological characteristics were manifest in the above-mentioned sense of spatial differentiation, as having a catalog of options to choose from as a teacher. For many, it is easier to ‘differentiate’ between different pupils (Paju; May; Li); as another student said, ‘it just gives many options as a teacher’ (Vilho).

As the classroom space was considered something ‘new’, its presence to student teachers became imbued with a temporal orientation towards the future. The classroom was depicted as ‘futuristic’ (Pyry), even ‘utopian’ (Tuisku). Here, students’ accounts find resonance with the idea of proto-practices operating as enactments of feasible utopias that embody something recognizable and familiar as well as something new (Suchman, Trigg and Blomberg, 2002). It seemed as if the encounter with the KAKS10 space incorporated a sense of the (feasible and attainable) future into the experiences of the students (Hönke and Cuesta Fernandez, 2017). This was highlighted in the experienced difference with other types of classrooms with which they were more familiar.

These accounts make apparent that a symbolic framing in the form of explicit zonal differentiation, or ‘recipes’ for how to use them, was not necessary for the continuous transformation of the main topological characteristics of the FCL prototype to emerge in students’ accounts.

Proto-practices and uncanny emotions

What stood out in the topological characterizations of KAKS10 was that they were often loaded with emotions. The classroom as a whole operated as a ‘sticky space’ (Laketa, 2018) as emotions frequently became fixed or adhered to in the classroom. Emotions also opened a repertoire of pedagogical actions for the students, in the sense that emotions were expressed to elicit (re)action from the students.

The emotions were wound around the above-mentioned characteristics of a prototype as something at once familiar and new. This explains why stickiness here bore the marks of *uncanniness*. The term uncanny refers to an encounter with something that has once been familiar which has since turned strange. Such an encounter is prone to elicit anxiety as it profoundly disorients an individual’s sense of reality or themselves (Royle, 2003). However, as Kraftl (2007) has highlighted,

uncanny encounters can also arouse excitement, especially when dealing with ‘utopian’ proto-practices, those which, while retaining something familiar (so as to be identifiable to begin with) also seem to ‘throw’ the subject into different future possibilities. This seems also to be the case in student teachers’ accounts, where the uncanny was mixed with a temporal ordering of the classroom and projections for certain kinds of pedagogical actions.

The reported first encounters among students with KAKS10 certainly express a mixture of the familiar and the unfamiliar in ways that did not seem to be planned or ‘programmed’ into the KAKS10 design by the teacher educators. For instance, the students reported recognizing KAKS10 as a classroom, many landmarks of what the student teachers considered a typical classroom are missing and, according to them, there are equally some disorienting characteristics in KAKS10. When asked about their impressions when they first entered the classroom, they expressed emotions of anxiety, excitement and trust which guided their initial orientation towards teaching. These were reportedly not clear and stable emotions, but rather diffuse and temporally vacillating. Members of one interview group all felt they experienced an initial shock-like reaction: ‘this is so different!’, which soon became mixed with the feeling of excitement (Mia; May; Li; Tuisku). Paju remembered being at once scared, because she had no clue about how teaching would take place in such an environment, but at the same time equally excited about what seemed to be innumerable pedagogical possibilities. She was also scared about the large number of children that would be present in the classroom. She remembered being completely overwhelmed with how the classroom looked: ‘What do you do with all those screens?!’ (Paju). For Tuisku and Pilvi, the room initially felt very overwhelming, equally given that there is no ‘closed’ space available. Quickly, however, the feeling came that ‘this is a lot of fun’.

Emotional responses were pervaded by a feeling of being pressured to do something ‘out of the ordinary’ or ‘non-traditional’ (Veini), and to use ‘technology’ (Vilho; Robin). It was as if the space itself called for a decisive break with one’s own past routines and ways of conceiving of teaching. This was highlighted as we explicitly asked whether this classroom had a ‘message’ for student teachers on how to teach. For many, it delivered the message that it was a good thing to use different teaching methods – the room ‘creates pressure or is conducive to using multiple methods’ (Tuisku), which differs from what they had done or experienced as pupils themselves (Tuisku; Pilvi; Robin)

These accounts testify to the way that emotions related to the uncanny experience of KAKS10 mediated some of the central elements of the proto-practice. They delivered the ideas of the FCL as a feasible utopia into the personal experiences of student teachers: KAKS10, while still experienced as a classroom, becomes recognized as ostensibly ‘different’ from ‘traditional’ classroom spaces; as *an already existing future space*. Moreover, the emotions charge the space with incentives to make certain pedagogical choices.

This way, different emotions of uncanniness resonate with the characteristics of a prototype as bearing the marks of the old and the familiar, as well as the new and the unknown. Moreover, these were anticipatory emotions – those directed at future events and actions – as KAKS10 is indeed a feasible utopia that pressures the student teachers to explore and try something new.

Dwelling in a proto-practice

Yet, the ways emotions do their work is still more complex, as there were even more detailed ‘partitionings’ of KAKS10 among the student teachers in their teaching practice. We sought to examine the transformation of the prototype into a proto-practice by systematically observing the behavior of student teachers in the classroom while marking their movements on the classroom floor plan. At the same time, we made notes on the pedagogical methods they used. In pair teaching, one of the teachers stood mainly next to the screen, talking to and instructing the pupils, who were seated in their chairs close to the screen. The other teacher moved around the classroom to supervise and support the pupils. Pupils were often instructed to work individually and in pairs in their own seats. It was less common to direct pupils to group or pair work in different parts of the classroom, such as the areas with sofas. Even rarer was the so-called ‘point work’, where pupils moved from one ‘point’ to another, completing a separate task at each location. The classroom amphitheater area was rarely used for teaching – only twice during the observation period.

During our interviews with students who taught in the KAKS10, we showed the students the class floor plan (without the zonal differentiation) and asked them to draw their movements in the classroom. We also told the student teachers about our findings (which resonated with the students’ drawings) and asked them to explain why they would use certain areas more than others. They often cited ‘practicality’, the fact that walls and chairs guide the placement of students in a certain way as a class, while technology guides teachers into certain positions. In addition, student teachers’ emotionally charged notions of what is normal, desirable and safe played a particular role.

Both the teacher educators and the students used the terms ‘White Room’ and ‘Red Room’ to refer to specific areas in the classroom for housing a class of pupils. The White Room was an area with round white tables for five pupils each (and which could be further separated into individual tables), while the Red Room was, in a sense, a classroom within a classroom – an area of tables organized into a U shape and separated by a wall and a glass door from the rest of the classroom (see [Figure 3](#)). The Red Room was frequently referred to as a ‘traditional classroom’ (Pilvi; Robin) or as a ‘classroom of the past’, with ‘traditional’ (Veini; May) pedagogy, mainly frontal, teacher-led instruction, while the area officially marked with Express and Influence zones was considered especially ‘new’ and conducive to non-traditional teaching methods (Vilho). Oftentimes student teachers mentioned their own experiences as pupils as a reference point of traditional classroom environments.

To some, the Red Room (of the past) spelt security and comfort as well as order (Pilvi, Vilho, Veini), to some it was ‘restrictive’, ‘boring’ and ‘stultifying’ (Tuisku, Pilvi). Moreover, the teacher’s desk in both the White Room and the Red Room was identified as a ‘comfortable area’ for many, while the ‘amphitheater-like area’ in the influence-express zone seemed to be somewhat overwhelming – ‘you need a special reason to use that’ (Veini), or to impart a feeling pressure to use it, but not knowing how. On the other hand, one of the interviewees mentioned the sofas and the arena as a specific area of comfort, and for ‘blending in’ or ‘mixing’ with the pupils (Tuisku).

As we can see, there is a very complex, emotionally loaded differentiation at work in the unofficial zoning at work in the proto-practice. Certain areas housed

a wide variety of emotions, from feelings of safety, overexcitement, to feeling threatened. Such zonings intersected with other differentiations, as some areas of the classroom were depicted as being more futuristic, and were described in more topological terms than others. This highlights that emotions, as they become attached to classroom spaces, have dispersed historical, personal, and cultural valence (Smith et al. 2009, 1). If the Red Room ‘feels safe’ as a reminder of a classroom of the past, it is not inscribed into the material space alone. Instead, it may hark back to an individual’s own memories of classroom spaces and narratives of who they are and will be as teachers, neither of which are purely private or personal in origin but emerged in past encounters with sociomaterial spaces and discourses which can then be projected onto the present classroom space (see also Cloke, May and Johnsen, 2008).

In sum, emotions ensure that the topological features of the prototype are communicated to the students as a space that is ‘new’ and suggests using non-traditional teaching methods in a flexible way. On the other hand, emotions also redistribute the variety of pedagogical methods in different areas in ways that do not fully follow the teacher educators’ original zonal model. This way, emotions mediate the prototype as a feasible utopia that encourages and demands experimentation with different teaching methods that differ from what students are used to, and what they perceive as ‘traditional’. Further, emotions give expression to the ambiguity of proto-practices – especially when students are not given precise instructions on how to interpret and use space, students’ varying emotions create varying possibilities for action.

Conclusion

In this article, we analyzed Future Classroom Labs as a *prototype* developed over time and assuming different forms across different locales, serving multiple functions, and turning into a *proto-practice*. On the one hand, we have argued that FCL exemplifies network governance, which is often studied as a paradigmatic form of topological policy culture (Lury, Parisi, and Terranova 2012, Gulson and Sellar, 2019; Terranova 2004). As we have shown, FCL brings together a wide array of policy actors from the public and private policy sectors. Instead of forcing uniformity and top-down structures, FCL seeks to respect and sustain the autonomy of its constituents. As such, it is a *remarkably soft* form of governance that equally enables communication and cooperation across different topographical locales (Lawn 2006). However, it is precisely in this ‘remarkable softness’ that the convincing character of governing by prototype(s) and -practice(s) lies, in the sense that this secures reach and influence through the allowing and even encouraging of local adaptation and transformation (cf. Allen, 2016). Furthermore, although our analysis followed the development of the FCL rationale from its initial ‘source’ in Belgium to national and local sites, this does not mean that there is a unilateral and uniform stream of influence reaching from the center to the periphery, or from macro to micro level (Allen, 2016). Instead, autonomy here means that the reach of topological governance is not secured by reducing topographical distance and cultural difference to ‘the same’, but rather cultivating *difference*, first, by inciting variation in relation to local exigencies and second, by including more (rather than less) spatiotemporal differentiation in the classroom compared to putatively ‘traditional’ classrooms. This ensures the topological

rationales of flexibility and mobility (Decuypere, Hartong, and van de Oudeweetering 2022).

Yet, on the other hand, we argue that considering FCL as an instantiation of remarkably soft network governance *alone* does not offer enough explanatory force to disentangle the agential work unique to the way FCL is realized. Considering FCL as a form of governing through prototype and proto-practice equally brings about characteristics rarely addressed in critical studies of topological policy cultures. Whereas framing prototypes as embedded in networked forms of governance allows for explaining the freedom that actors have in adopting the prototype, and the differences that are explicitly promoted to exist between various local enactments of the prototype (and subsequent proto-practices), governing by prototype and -practice accounts for, and highlights, the painstaking processes of repetition and variation established in relation to a highly specific idea or concept – and it is especially the latter that is seldom analyzed when adopting the lens of network governance (cf. Gulson and Sellar 2019).

Lastly, our analysis showcased how, in cases where teachers are given no guidelines on how to use the prototype, the role of emotions in how prototypes are interpreted and experimented with in pedagogical proto-practices. First of all, emotions are involved in the ways teachers interpret the topological features of FCL classrooms. Second, our analysis suggests that emotions delimit how FCL prototypes are divided into different areas and linked to pedagogical practices – often in unexpected ways. For instance, the emotionally felt uncanniness of FCL space may lead student teachers to avoid certain spaces as uncomfortable. However, unhomey feelings may also have a productively unsettling effect (Kraftl 2007): being thrown into unknown environments produces disruption of habit and comfort, and can sensitize the teacher to unforeseen and open-ended possibilities of being in a proto-practice. Indeed, feelings of excitement which encouraged to try what is new and unknown, were also present in student teacher accounts. Even though they seem to play a decisive role in how prototypes are formed and into how one dwells into proto-practices, such aspects are currently understudied in research on topological policy cultures. As such, this article shows the importance for critical policy researchers employing a topological lens to take the affective and emotional realm of practices into account as well – something that is currently only done in piecemeal manner.

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